
Policy Brief

February
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Improving Adult Literacy for Social Inclusion and Economic Growth:

Strategic Actions,
Stakeholder Engagement,
and Future Perspectives

Key Messages

- Illiteracy can cost developed countries up to 2% of GDP each year. A 1% increase in adult literacy is linked to a 3% rise in GDP per capita, underscoring the strong link between workforce literacy and economic growth.
- Adult Learning and Vocation Educational Training centres are key structures in the development of reading skills among the adult population; however, teachers and trainers struggle with a lack of dedicated resources and appropriate materials.
- Users and field professionals are essential to ensuring that technology remains relevant and effective. Responsible technology developed cooperatively with end users can help bridge the gap between skills and labour market demands, promoting adaptability and confidence.
- Empowering adults to read more, without social stigma and while respecting their individual interests, opens new pathways to knowledge, culture and arts, and creates market opportunities for cultural and educational activities.

“Responsible technology developed cooperatively with end users can help bridge the gap between skills and labour market demands, promoting adaptability and confidence.”

- Textual complexity is a feature of texts; it does not reflect the value or literary quality of the content. A structured complexity-based classification of works, supporting discoverability, reader confidence, and literacy progression, contributes to widening readership, particularly among adults with emerging or intermediate reading skills, and expands the potential market for and written information.

Background and Context

The iRead4Skills project aligns directly with the European Skills Agenda and the Upskilling Pathways initiative, which recognize **literacy as a foundational skill for employability, inclusion, and lifelong learning**. Despite existing efforts, over 73 million adults in the EU still lack basic literacy, numeracy, and digital skills. Low literacy hinders active citizenship, economic participation, and access to services, leading to increased inequality

Reading skills are fundamental to acquire technical and scientific knowledge, either in formal education and training contexts, as Adult Learning (AL) and Vocational Educational Training (VET), or in practical and empirical working contexts, as when companies provide written specific information and/or instructions to their workers. However, promoting and motivating reading habits and skills in adults is quite challenging due to the lack of dedicated and/or adequate reading materials.

1. The Economic and Social Costs of Low Literacy

Low literacy generates direct and indirect economic burdens. The World Literacy Foundation (2015) estimates that illiteracy costs developed nations up to 2% of GDP annually due to lost earnings, reduced business productivity, missed wealth-creation opportunities, and inadequate high-tech skills capacity. According to IZA/OECD research, a 1% increase in adult literacy skills is associated with a 3% increase in GDP per capita, underscoring the strong link between workforce literacy and economic output.

Beyond economics, the social cost includes increased health inequalities, intergenerational transmission of low education, and disengagement from civic life. Investing in adult literacy is therefore both a social imperative and an economic strategy.

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1. The Economic and Social Costs of Low Literacy

Average score on a 0–500 scale (OECD avg: 260)

Key finding: Portugal has the lowest adult literacy levels in Europe (PIAAC score: 235), with approximately 40% of adults scoring at Level 1 or below – compared to 26% for the EU average. These gaps translate directly into lost economic output estimated at up to 2% of GDP per year.

PORTUGAL

235

PIAAC Score

= 2% GDP

Est. annual loss

SPAIN

250

PIAAC Score

= 2% GDP

Est. annual loss

FRANCE

255

PIAAC Score

= 2% GDP

Est. annual loss

EU AVERAGE

260

PIAAC Score

= 2% GDP

Est. annual loss

Sources: World Literacy Foundation, "The Economic & Social Cost of Illiteracy" (2025); OECD, "Survey of Adult Skills (PIAAC) 2023" (December 2024); EU average approximated from OECD mean (260 points). GDP loss estimates based on WLF model: 2% of GDP for developed nations.

2. The iRead4Skills project

Supporting the adoption and diffusion of innovation in adult education and training, the iRead4Skills project aims to promote the development of reading skills through an innovative intelligent system that evaluates text complexity and suggests reading materials adequate to the user reading level. The system can also support the creation or adaptation of texts to match the appropriate level of complexity for their target audiences.

In doing so, the project contributes:

- to the upskilling and reskilling of adults;
- to the development of new educational strategies within formal education, responding to both individual and social needs and boosting adults' motivation and participation;
- to more innovative and inclusive education systems, leveraging digital technologies to provide quality training.

By bringing together an interdisciplinarity team covering Computer Sciences, ICT, Linguistics, Economics and Education, the project delivers research and innovation that go beyond the current state of the art in several key areas:

- Identifying and responding to the specific needs of AL and VET communities, and developing evaluation frameworks to inform employers and policymakers;

- Designing new complexity measures and foundational datasets;
- Developing and testing Natural Language Processing systems directly with end users;
- Promoting the use of Arts and Culture as vehicles for developing fundamental and transversal skills.

The project's most tangible outcome is the iRead4Skills system—an open-access, web-based ICT platform capable of providing:

- i) an overall complexity classification of any text;
- ii) a comprehensive and transparent analysis of complexity indicators;
- iii) scientifically grounded assistance in text simplification.

The uniqueness of iRead4Skills lies in its interdisciplinary foundation and its close collaboration with end-users, particularly AL and VET trainers and adults with low literacy skills. This approach ensures that the system responds to real needs while enabling an innovative framework for developing and validating machine-learning models. Unlike many existing tools, iRead4Skills specifically addresses issues of textual complexity for adult native speakers.

Evidence from iRead4Skills

1. Survey Findings

- 84% of low-literate adults reported difficulties understanding essential documents (health instructions, job ads, legal forms).
- Literacy deficits directly impacted transversal skills: 68% reported difficulties with digital tasks; 59% with numeracy.
- Pilot testing showed significant improvements in reading comprehension and digital skills among participants.

2. Project Impact and User Feedback

Training activities reached over 420 educators, with participants from Portugal, Brazil, Angola, Guinea-Bissau, and Mozambique. Feedback from the December 2025 training session was highly positive, with teachers highlighting the tool's intuitive interface and pedagogical value. European-wide tools testing across Belgium, Portugal, and Spain engaged 423 participants (304 adult learners and 119 teachers/trainers) with consistently high satisfaction levels across all three countries.

In total, the activities developed for user engagement reached more than 890 participants world-wide

The iRead4Skills Conference - A New Journey Through Knowledge, which took place in Lisbon on 25 February 2026, gathered more than 450 participants to discuss key project results and findings, as well as future perspectives on adult literacy and skills development.

Invited speakers included Simone Rosini (European Commission's Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion) and Valentina Stoeva (President of EURead - The European Reading Promotion and Literacy Network), who shared insights on the strategic role of reading as a prerequisite for future skills, highlighting how empowering children begins with supporting adults to read more.

The conference also featured numerous testimonies from AL and VET teachers and students, as well as librarians and publishers from Portugal, Spain, and Belgium.

3. Research Impact

In 2024-2026, the project produced over of 30 peer-reviewed research publications, organized a journal special issue and a scientific workshop dedicated to readability and complexity analysis.

It released several linguistic resources and datasets, as well and technical reports.

Evidence from iRead4Skills

4. International and National Network Collaboration

iRead4Skills has established and maintained productive collaborations with key European institutions, including:

- **EBSN (European Basic Skills Network):** iRead4Skills became a member of EBSN in **July 2023**, joining a network of ministries of education, universities, research centres, and NGOs committed to promoting excellence in basic skills policy. Since then, the project presented results at the **EBSN Annual Conferences in 2024 and 2025**, and the consortium leader is hosting the conference in 2026.
- **EPALE (Electronic Platform for Adult Learning in Europe):** Regular dissemination of project outcomes and active participation in the platform's community discussions on adult literacy innovation, ensuring visibility among European adult education practitioners.
- The project has also conducted successful meetings with the **FEP-FEE (Federation of European Publishers)**, **APEL (Portuguese National Publishers Association)** and **DGLAB (General Directorate of Books, Archives and Libraries)** for future engagement and cooperation.

5. Stakeholder Roles and Actions

National Ministries (Education, Labour, Digital Transition)

Integrate literacy with national employment and digital agendas; fund regional roll-outs of literacy tools in AL and VET centres; include literacy targets in National Recovery and Resilience Plan.

Adult Learning and Vocation Educational Training Providers

Embed complexity-assessment technology in basic skills courses; offer blended literacy training using digital platforms; collect and share learner progress data to inform national policy.

Employers

Conduct workplace literacy audits; provide in-house basic skills training using iRead4Skills; co-invest with public institutions in employee upskilling programs.

Policy Recommendations

Recommendations to align national strategies with key EU policy frameworks, including the **European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan** (2030 targets), the **European Skills Agenda 2020-2025**, the **Union of Skills** initiative (March 2025), and the **New European Agenda for Adult Learning 2021-2030**.

1. Mainstream literacy into national skills strategies: Align with the European Pillar of Social Rights target of **60% adult participation in training annually by 2030**. Integrate literacy objectives into National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRPs) and European Semester reporting. Follow the **Upskilling Pathways** recommendation's three-step approach: skills assessment, tailored learning offer, and validation/recognition.

2. Deploy intelligent reading systems: Support the **Digital Decade** target of **80% of adults with basic digital skills by 2030**. Use AI-enhanced tools like iRead4Skills to personalise content by proficiency level, addressing the Commission's **Action Plan on Basic Skills** (March 2025) call for targeted interventions for underachieving groups.

3. Create funding incentives for employers and VET centres:

Leverage ESF+, Erasmus+, and the **Recovery and Resilience Facility** for literacy programmes. Engage employers through the **Pact for Skills**, which has mobilised over 2,000 organisations committed to workforce upskilling. Support workplace literacy audits and in-house training co-investment.

4. Track literacy gains and economic returns: Use **PIAAC** (Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competences) data and the **Education and Training Monitor** indicators for performance-based policy evaluation. Report progress through the European Semester's Social Scoreboard, contributing to evidence-informed policymaking as outlined in the Council Resolution on adult learning.

5. Foster cross-border collaboration: Strengthen partnerships through **EPALE**, **EBSN**, and **Erasmus+** strategic partnerships. Align with the **Union of Skills** framework's emphasis on skills portability and the recognition of micro-credentials across Member States. Support the **European Education Area** vision of seamless learning mobility. **Integrate research engagement into the formal roles and responsibilities of AL and VET professionals.**

Sustainability and Future Perspectives

The iRead4Skills consortium continues to pursue sustainability pathways to ensure the project's impact extends beyond the current funding period:

- **Horizon Europe Booster Programme:**

The project has been engaged with the Horizon Europe Results Booster, which provides dedicated support for scaling and exploiting research results. This programme will facilitate the transition from pilot testing to wider deployment and market access.

- **Follow-up Funding Applications:**

The consortium is preparing applications for subsequent EU funding calls, including the EIC Transition Programme,

the Digital Europe Programme and Erasmus+ strategic partnerships, to continue development and expand language coverage.

- **Open Access Resources:** All project deliverables, including the text complexity classification system, will remain freely available in <https://iread4skills.com/tools-resources/> and <https://zenodo.org/communities/iread4skills>, ensuring continued benefit to the adult learning community.

The iRead4Skills tools can be accessed here:

<https://iread4skills.com/tools/>

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